

MODERN IDEAS ON THERAPEUTIC WORKOUTS TO GET RID OF RHINOLALIA AFTER SURGERY

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Annotation

In this article, we've looked at the method of corrective work done with rhinoceros kids in the immediate post-operative period, the uniqueness of their speech, the significance of logopedic rhythms, and the therapeutic exercises done one at a time during the corrective process.

Key words

rhinolalia, preoperative period, postoperative period, breathing exercises, articulatory apparatus, articulatory exercises, lip exercises, palatal exercises, palatal-laryngeal exercises, larynx exercises.

In the postoperative period, there are several types of therapeutic exercises to eliminate rhinolalia. These include articulation exercises, breathing exercises, massage, etc. Now we will consider some of them. Below are some examples of articulation exercises.

Children with cleft lip and palate (rhinolalia) have a tendency for the mass of the tongue to move back into the oral cavity. As a result, articulation occurs mainly in the throat region and at the root of the tongue; the tip of the tongue does not participate in sound production. The root of the tongue of children with rhinolalia develops in its strength and size, but cannot make the fine, differentiated movements necessary for the formation of speech sounds.

Therefore, when conducting language gymnastics, special attention is paid to the following:

- stimulating the movements of the tip of the tongue, the front-middle and back parts of the back of the tongue;
- transfer of the articular focus to the front sections of the oral resonator;
- development of differentiated kinesthetic perception;
- strengthening of the entire muscle background for the upcoming uranoplasty (palatoplasty).

Articulatory exercises to stimulate the movement of the tip of the tongue outside the mouth

1. Put your tongue between your lips.
2. Pull the tip of the tongue towards the nose.
3. Pull the tip of the tongue to the chin.
4. Touch the tip of the tongue to the right corner of the mouth and fix this position.
5. Touch the tongue to the left corner of the mouth and fix this position.
6. Touch the tip of the tongue to the upper lip and fix this position.
7. Touch the tip of the tongue to the lower lip and fix this position.
8. Move the tip of the tongue along the upper lip (imitating lip licking).
9. Move the tip of the tongue along the lower lip.
10. Make a circular motion with the tip of the tongue along the upper and lower lip.
11. Forcefully squeeze the tongue between the teeth so that the upper incisors touch the back of the tongue.

Exercises are performed first slowly, then at medium speed, fixing the position of the tongue. Each articular pose is held for a certain time (counting from 1 to 5) to strengthen the tongue muscles.

Articulatory exercises to develop the accuracy of the movements of the tip of the tongue inside the mouth.

The mouth is wide open.

1. Touch the tip of the tongue to the lower incisors.
2. Touch the tip of the tongue to the upper incisors.
3. Touching the tip of the tongue to the alveoli.
4. Touch the upper alveoli with the tip of the tongue repeatedly and pronounce the sound t: t-t-t.
5. Touch the alveoli with the tip of the tongue repeatedly and pronounce the d sound: d-d-d.

Articulatory exercises for dynamic organization of movements of the tip of the tongue outside the mouth

1. Touch the tongue to the chin, then to the nose.
2. Pull the tongue to the chin, then touch the tip of the tongue to the upper lip.
3. Pull the tongue to the chin, then touch the tip of the tongue to the right corner of the mouth.
4. Pull the tongue to the jaw, then touch the tip of the tongue to the left corner of the mouth.

5. Pull the tongue to the jaw, then move the tip of the tongue along the upper lip (imitation of lip licking).

6. Pull the tongue up to the chin, then make circular movements with the tip of the tongue along the upper and lower lip.

7. Pull the tongue to the chin, then fix the tip of the tongue to the lower incisors.

8. Move the tongue to the right and left (imitating the movement of the keyboard).

9. Pull the tongue to the chin, nose, touch the tip of the tongue to the upper lip.

10. Pull the tongue to the chin, nose, move the tip of the tongue along the upper lip.

11. Pull the tongue to the chin, nose, touch the tip of the tongue to the right corner of the mouth.

12. Pull the tongue to the chin, nose, touch the tip of the tongue to the left corner of the mouth.

13. Pull the tongue to the chin, nose, fix the tip of the tongue to the lower incisors.

Articulatory exercises for dynamic movement of the tip of the tongue.

The mouth is wide open.

1. Touch the tip of the tongue to the lower teeth, and then to the upper teeth.

2. Touching the tip of the tongue to the lower teeth, and then to the alveoli.

3. Touch the tip of the tongue to the lower teeth first from the inside, then from the outside.

4. Touch the tip of the tongue to the upper part of the alveolus, first from the inside, then from the outside.

5. The tip of the tongue is brought under the upper lip and pulled back and forth into the mouth, coming out with a click.

6. The tip of the tongue is attached to the lower teeth, and then rests on the right cheek.

7. The tip of the tongue is attached to the lower teeth, then rests on the left cheek.

These exercises not only develop mobility, the accuracy of the movements of the tip of the tongue, the ability to move from one movement to another, but also prepare the conditions for the transfer of articular attention from the back parts of the oral resonator to the front parts. Children begin to actively use the muscles of the tip of the tongue.

Articulatory exercises for the development of mobility, accuracy of the movements of the front-middle and back parts of the back of the tongue.

1. The tip of the tongue rests on the lower gum, and the front-middle part of the back of the tongue rises.

2. The tip of the tongue rests on the alveolus of the lower teeth, and the front-middle part of the back of the tongue rises until it touches the upper teeth.

3. Stretching the front part of the back of the tongue forward (the tongue seems to fall out of the mouth); attach the tip of the tongue to the lower teeth.

4. Raising the back of the tongue while opening the mouth wide at the same time; attach the tip of the tongue to the lower teeth.

While the child performs the listed exercises, the speech therapist carefully monitors the attachment of the tip of the tongue to the lower teeth (each articular position is counted from 1 to 5).

Articulatory exercises for the dynamic organization of the movements of the front-middle and back parts of the back of the tongue.

1. Raise and lower the front-middle part of the back of the tongue; the tip of the tongue rests on the lower gum, the front-middle part of the back of the tongue either rises or falls, as in pronouncing the sound a.

2. Raise and lower the back of the tongue; the tip of the tongue rests on the lower gums, and the back of the tongue rises and falls.

3. Pulling the tongue out of the mouth as far as possible, and then pulling it into the mouth as far as possible.

Articulatory exercises for dynamic organization of tongue and jaw movements

1. Touch the tip of the tongue to the lower teeth and open the mouth wide.

2. Fasten the tip of the tongue to the lower teeth and yawn widely.

3. Fix the tip of the tongue to the lower teeth, open your mouth wide and yawn.

4. Touch the tip of the tongue to the upper alveolus and open the mouth wide.

5. Touch the tip of the tongue to the alveoli and open your mouth wide.

6. Touch the tip of the tongue to the upper alveolus, open your mouth and yawn widely.

7. Touch the tip of the tongue to the lower alveoli, open your mouth wide and yawn.

8. The tip of the tongue is attached to the lower teeth, and the front-middle part of the back of the tongue rises up with the jaw dropping sharply.

9. Circular movements with the tip of the tongue along the upper lip with gradual opening of the mouth.

Articulatory exercises for dynamic organization of tongue and lip movements

1. The tip of the tongue is attached to the lower teeth, and the lips take an articulate position: they are widely rounded, as when pronouncing the sound a; to stretch wide, as with and; elongated and rounded as in e; extended with a wide tube, as with y.

2. The tip of the tongue is attached to the upper teeth, and the lips occupy the listed articulation positions.

3. The tip of the tongue is fixed in the alveoli, and the lips take the listed articulation positions.

The correctness of each movement is controlled by reflection in the mirror and comparison with the model (the speech therapist demonstrates each movement). Exercises are performed in front of a mirror based on kinesthetic and tactile stimulation.

Coordination of tongue and jaw movements and exhalation exercises

1. Fix the tip of the tongue to the lower incisors, open your mouth wide and exhale for a long time.

2. Raise the tip of the tongue to the alveoli, open the mouth wide and exhale for a long time.

3. Fix the tip of the tongue to the lower teeth, raise the front-middle part of the back of the tongue, open the mouth wide and exhale.

4. Fix the tip of the tongue to the lower teeth, raise the back of the tongue, open the mouth wide and exhale for a long time.

Articulatory exercises for coordination of tongue and lips and coordination movements

Attach the tip of the tongue to the lower teeth.

1. Open your mouth wide and exhale for a long time, as in the sound A.

2. Stretch your lips into a smile, as in the sound, and exhale for a long time.

3. Exhale for a long time by curling the lips as in the sound O.

4. Pull your lips forward with a pipe as in the sound of y and take a long breath.

5. Pull the lips forward, make a round like the sound e and exhale long.

Attach the tip of the tongue to the upper teeth.

1. Open your mouth wide and exhale for a long time, as in the sound A.

2. Stretch your lips into a smile, as in the sound, and exhale for a long time.

3. Exhale for a long time by curling the lips as in the sound O.

4. Pull your lips forward with a pipe as in the sound of y and take a long breath.

5. Attach the tip of the tongue to the alveoli, perform the listed positions of the lips and exhale.

Each exercise is performed first with closed nasal passages, then alternately with closed and open nasal passages, and finally with open nasal passages. Exercises are performed under the control of visual, tactile and muscle sensations. The child develops proper coordination by comparing the strength and duration of the air stream released by the speech therapist and himself.

For the development of differential kinesthetic perception, exercises with sharply contrasting properties are selected, then for less contrasting movements. The articulatory positions necessary for the production of sounds that need correction in the future are developed.

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